

Linear viscoelasticity of concentrated polyethylene glycol tert-octylphenyl ether solutions

Moros, J.E.¹; Cordobés, F.¹; Gallegos, C.²; Franco J.M.² (2001).

¹ Department of Chemical Engineering, Universidad de Sevilla, Sevilla, Spain.

² Department of Chemical Engineering, ETSI, Universidad de Huelva, Huelva, Spain.

Journal Dispersion Science and Technology, 22, 409-420. ISSN: 0193-2691.

DOI: 10.1081/DIS-100107850

Abstract: Linear viscoelastic studies were carried out on concentrated polyethylene glycol tert-octylphenyl ether solutions over a range of temperatures and concentrations comprising the lamellar and hexagonal liquid-crystalline phases and the isotropic surfactant-rich phase. The generalized or a simple Maxwell model fits the frequency dependence of the dynamic functions for the hexagonal and isotropic surfactant-rich phases, respectively. The combined influence of temperature and concentration on both the zero-shear rate-limiting viscosity and the relaxation time for isotropic samples follows an exponential dependence. The results are discussed according to the phase behaviour of these systems.

Key words: Viscoelasticity; Polyethylene glycol t-octylphenol ether; Maxwell model; Phase diagrams; Hexagonal phase; Cubic phase; Lamellar phase.